

S1 Raw Images A.

Full uncropped gel from S1B Fig.

S1 Raw Images B.

Full uncropped gel from S6B Fig. (lanes 1-15) and from S7B Fig. (lanes 17-20)

Gel	Lane	Content
A	1	1kb Plus DNA Ladder (New England BioLabs, #N3200)
	2	S/+ mouse genomic DNA amplified with LHom-F/R
	3	S/+ mouse genomic DNA amplified with RHom-F/R
	4	Not loaded
	5	Not loaded
	6	Not loaded
B	1	1kb Plus DNA Ladder (New England BioLabs, #N3200)
	2	Male family 2a genomic DNA amplified with CC F1/Tyr HAR R2
	3	Male family 2b genomic DNA amplified with CC F1/Tyr HAR R2
	4	Male family 2c genomic DNA amplified with CC F1/Tyr HAR R2
	5	Male family 3 genomic DNA amplified with CC F1/Tyr HAR R2
	6	Male family 4 genomic DNA amplified with CC F1/Tyr HAR R2
	7	Male family 5a genomic DNA amplified with CC F1/Tyr HAR R2
	8	Male family 5b genomic DNA amplified with CC F1/Tyr HAR R2
	9	Male family 5c genomic DNA amplified with CC F1/Tyr HAR R2
	10	Female family 1 genomic DNA amplified with CC F1/Tyr HAR R2
	11	1kb Plus DNA Ladder (New England BioLabs, #N3200)
	12	Female family 4a genomic DNA amplified with CC F1/Tyr HAR R2
	13	Female family 4b genomic DNA amplified with CC F1/Tyr HAR R2
	14	Female family 4c genomic DNA amplified with CC F1/Tyr HAR R2
15	WT genomic DNA amplified with CC F1/Tyr HAR R2	
16	Not loaded	
17	1kb Plus DNA Ladder (New England BioLabs, #N3200)	
18	WT genomic DNA amplified with Spo11-In-F/Spo11-Out-F/Spo11-Out-R	
19	S/+ genomic DNA amplified with Spo11-In-F/Spo11-Out-F/Spo11-Out-R	
20	S/S genomic DNA amplified with Spo11-In-F/Spo11-Out-F/Spo11-Out-R	

Table of lane contents associated with images A and B.

S1 Raw Image C.

Full uncropped gels that are the same as shown in S2 Fig.

(A-C) Western blot of (A) SPO11, (B) CAS9, and (C) eGFP on three wild type and three *Spo11^{Cas9-P2A-eGFP/+}* adult testes. **(A'-C')** Serially-stained membranes adding anti β -ACTIN to detect the loading control.

PP, Precision Plus Ladder; MM, MagicMark Ladder.